

THE ROLE OF DIPLOMATIC LANGUAGE IN THE LANGUAGE SYSTEM AND THE ANALYSIS OF DIPLOMATIC TERMS

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Abstract. *Despite a significant number of scientific works devoted to terms and terminologies, interest in this subject of research does not fade away. This fact is explained by the constant development of various spheres of human life, the emergence of new technologies, inventions and scientific knowledge. This article discusses the role of diplomatic terms in the language system.*

Keywords: *terminology, term, one-word terms, terminological system, diplomatic language.*

INTRODUCTION

Until now, there is no single, generally accepted definition of the term "term" [1, p. 20]. In the Big Encyclopedic Dictionary. Linguistics" term (from Latin terminus 'boundary, limit') is defined as a word or phrase that denotes the concept of any field of knowledge or field of activity [2, p. 508].

MATERIALS AND METHODS

V.P. Danilenko believes that the term refers to a special area of use and is the name of a special concept [3, p. 15].

In general, most definitions agree that a term is a word (or phrase) characteristic of a certain field of activity, which serves to designate a special concept.

Terminology is understood as a set of terms (a kind of ordered system of terms) of a certain activity, industry or knowledge [4, p. 62].

Diplomacy is an important tool in the foreign policy of any state. The training of highly qualified specialists of the diplomatic service requires knowledge of the basic terms of the protocol and etiquette of international communication.

As for the definitions of the term, they change over time, but the provisions put forward by D.S. Lotte, remain generally accepted:

- 1) the term is considered as a member of the national terminological system;
- 2) a term element is a minimal unit that has a terminological meaning and participates in term formation;
- 3) naturally formed terminologies have certain "shortcomings";
- 4) "absolute" and "relative" unambiguity of terms are distinguished;
- 5) it is necessary to divide the array of concepts into "own" and "attracted" (only the terms of own concepts are ordered);
- 6) initially, the status of a terminological recommendation should be given to the ordered terms, so that specialists get used to the new understanding of the terms;

7) first of all, attention should be paid to the correct construction of term nodes that are producer terms, because the entire structure of their own industry terminology depends on their structure;

8) the formed term must be a proper name of an object or concept, not having synonyms in the given area and not representing a homonym;

9) an existing and newly created term should cause a certain association - “private” (semantic) or “nodal” (aggregate).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The very concept of "diplomatic language" means two concepts. Firstly, it is the language in which official diplomatic negotiations are held, as well as international treaties are drawn up. It's no secret that the first language of diplomacy was Latin, which was replaced by French. In the modern world, there is a tendency towards equality of languages. Secondly, it is a set of terms related to the sphere of diplomacy.

Diplomatic terminology is a complex dynamic system that includes the terms of such spheres of diplomacy as diplomatic service, diplomatic law, diplomatic protocol, diplomatic etiquette, etc. ranks, diplomatic documents, diplomatic procedures, diplomatic visits, diplomatic missions, diplomatic rights and privileges, diplomatic receptions, etc.

The group "diplomatic agents / diplomatic ranks" 'positions and diplomatic ranks' includes, for example, such terms as ambassador, ambassador extraordinary, ambassador extraordinary and plenipotentiary, attaché, chargé d'affaires, consul, consul general, counselor, diplomat, doyen, envoy, legate, minister plenipotentiary, nuncio, vice-consul, etc.

The terminological group "diplomatic documents" includes, for example, the names of such diplomatic documents as accord 'agreement', aide-mémoire 'memorandum, memo', concordat 'agreement between individuals, governments', contract 'agreement', convention, credentials (letters of credence) 'credentials (of the ambassador)', letters of recall 'letters of recall', note verbal, procès-verbal 'protocol', etc.

The names of diplomatic missions are combined into the group "diplomatic bodies": chancellery 'the building where the chancellor and his subordinates work', 'consulate', 'embassy', consulate general, High Commission and etc.

The “diplomatic procedures” group combines the names of various diplomatic procedures: accession (to a treaty, convention), accreditation (diplomatic representatives), arbitration 'arbitration court', diplomatic asylum, démarche, denunciation 'termination (of a treaty)', exequatur (certificate of recognition of a foreign consul), extradition 'extradition to a foreign state of a criminal', ratification, etc.

The terminological group "diplomatic privileges and immunities" includes, for example, such names as extritoriality, inviolability of person, inviolability of domicile, exemption from local taxation, exemption (from local criminal and civil jurisdiction), etc.

The group "diplomatic receptions" includes the names of various types of diplomatic receptions (official / unofficial; daytime / evening; with seating / without seating): a glass of wine, a glass of champagne, breakfast, lunch buffet, dinner, cocktail, "Jour fixe", tea and coffee, etc. [5, pp. 116–118].

In addition to the above groups that make up the terminological field "Diplomacy", there are other groups and subgroups of terms that require further more detailed study and description.

An important distinguishing feature of diplomatic terminology is the presence of numerous names of Latin and French origin. As noted above, these languages played the role of a diplomatic language in the early periods of the development of diplomacy as an important tool for peacefully regulating international disputes.

Among the Latin terms, the following can be mentioned: *ad honorarium*, *ad interim* 'temporary', *a priori* 'before experience, speculative', e.g. (*exempli gratia*) 'for example', *in status quo* 'in the present state', *mutatis mutandis* 'with appropriate, necessary changes', *nolens-volens* 'by necessity', *via* 'through (someone's) mediation, through', *videlicet (viz)* 'precisely; i.e., for example, etc.

One example of the use of French names in diplomatic protocol is the generally accepted international practice of abbreviations, which are written in pencil in the lower left corner of business cards to express the relationship to the person to whom this card is given: *p. r.* (*pour remercier*) 'expresses gratitude', *p. f.* (*pour féliciter*) 'congratulates', *p. c.* (*pour condoléance*) 'expresses condolences', *p.p.c.* (*pour prendre congé*) 'as a token of farewell', etc. [5, p. 178].

In the term system under study, according to the structural classification, two types of diplomatic terms can be distinguished: terms-words (*accreditation*, *extradition*, *consulate*) and terms-phrases (multi-component terms) (*acte final* 'final act (meetings, conferences)', *ambassador-at-large* 'ambassador with wide powers', *chargé d'affaires ad interim* 'chargé d'affaires', *envoy extraordinary* and *minister plenipotentiary* 'ambassador extraordinary and plenipotentiary', etc.).

CONCLUSION

In the terminology of the sphere of diplomacy of both Russian and English, the number of phrases exceeds the number of single-word terms, which is explained by the fact that phrases more accurately express the meaning of the concept, i.e. they are characterized by a large specialization of meaning.

Summarizing the above information, we can conclude that diplomatic terminology has a number of common features inherent in all terminological systems and a number of features. Like any term system, it consists of a number of terminological groups and subgroups, the elements of which are closely related to each other by a common meaning. We identified such main groups of terms as diplomatic representatives / ranks, diplomatic documents, diplomatic procedures, diplomatic missions, diplomatic privileges, diplomatic receptions, etc. It was also noted that an important distinguishing feature of diplomatic terminology is the presence of numerous names of Latin and French origin. According to the structural classification, two types of diplomatic terms were distinguished: terms-words and terms-phrases.

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